

EASTERN FOLK TRADITIONS AS A MEANS OF LEGAL AND
CULTURAL UPBRINGING OF CHILDREN

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Annotation: *Folk pedagogy has great potential in the legal and cultural upbringing of children. Folk traditions ensure legal and cultural upbringing of children: careful treatment of them, excluding physical punishment, combining love, trust in them and strict observance of their duties; instilling in them since childhood a respectful attitude towards parents and elders, which promotes the connection between generations; attachment to native places, which fosters careful attitude towards nature, towards people of their land, providing basis for formation and development of patriotic feelings; effortless participation of children in different kinds of home A brief review of folk traditions, based on the example of the Uzbeks, shows that they function as a means of legal education, as traditions of different peoples contain information necessary to develop the inner world of the student's personality; traditions are learned through image, visual and practical, or sign-signal (oral or written) means; traditions in the joint activity of the teacher and students provide the most important, namely, controllability of the process of legal education. Manageability is created when: education is an organic part, a natural component of real life and performed in the process of solving life tasks; national traditions, acting as principles, standards, ideals, rules, creating public opinion, develop certain algorithms of human behavior, regulating his vital activity.*

Key words: *education, legal education of children, legal culture, folk pedagogy, educational traditions, customs, customary law, traditions, family, family education, lawful behavior, means of education.*

Folk traditions carry a great potential of legal and cultural content, which makes it possible to use them as a means of legal education for children. Legal concepts, provisions, beliefs, rules of life, principles reflected in the folklore of different peoples, this is what can be the basis of legal morality. A person must know and understand the

system of such absolute values as personality, freedom, life, on which his rights are based, in order to realize them. Legal and cultural education of children consists in their understanding of the meaning of their behavior, the ability to act in society in interaction with the rules of law, moral rules.

Moral experience of past generations, cultural and other needs of society are the basis of any legal system. Therefore, traditional pedagogy provides a unique opportunity to address modern pedagogical challenges: mastering the younger generation standards of behavior in society, the norms of morality, promoting self-fulfillment, the development of practical skills of social action. And this, in turn, plays a special role in the process of legal socialization, purposefully forming a full member of society, able to navigate the legal environment, to act with an understanding of the responsibility for their actions, decisions. Therefore, an appeal to the socio-cultural norms of society, to the national experience, to folk traditions is important both in the content and in the process of legal education of modern children. Even K.D. Ushinsky noted: "Education, if it does not want to be powerless, must be popular, it must be permeated with nationality". [1, c. 162]. The problem of legal-cultural education has been studied and is being studied by various scientists: teachers, psychologists, sociologists, philosophers, lawyers. In the process of developing the theory of legal education, means of its practical implementation was carried out development of various problems. Modern concepts of legal education, social value of the right are disclosed in the works of lawyers S. S. Alekseev [2], V. S. Nersesyants [3]. The organization of legal education of teachers and students with appropriate methodological support of teaching is considered by G. P. Davydov [4], A. Y. Azarov [5]. The content and organization of the process of legal education is devoted to the work of I.F. Ryabko [6]. E. A. Lukasheva [7], L. M. Kornienko [8] defined legal consciousness as a result of purposeful legal education in their works. An important place belongs to the works of A.F. Nikitin on the education of the legal culture of young people, V.M. Obukhov on the formation of the social and legal experience of students in the whole educational process through moral and legal education. More specific problems associated with the mechanism of awareness and assimilation of legal norms by students, the peculiarities of legal educational activities are considered in the works of V.A. Baluk, V.G. Podzolkov [9].

In recent years, there have been many dissertation studies in the field of moral and legal education by E.A. Andreeva [10], V.E. Semenov [11] and others. The works of R.I. Balkarov [12], M.G. Lavarslanova [13] are of particular interest and importance for understanding the studied problem from the perspective of the ethnoregional approach. Despite the significant number of works on the problem under study, the issues of legal education of children on the basis of folk pedagogy remain insufficiently studied. Folk pedagogy as a spiritual reality of people's existence represents a certain amount of pedagogical information embodied in the folk wisdom, in preconceptions, ideas, judgments, rules, habits, oral folk art (byliny, tales, fairy tales, parables, proverbs, proverbs, folk songs, rites, customs, traditions, etc.) relating to training and

education of people formed historically and spontaneously. In a certain sense it is the expression of historical memory of the nation, in particular in issues of upbringing of the new generation and behavior. The totality of phenomena of folk pedagogy affects the solution of legal tasks indirectly: through folk traditions, moral preaching of religious culture, legal experience of behavior and activity of representatives of the past, etc. They concentrate the best features of personality and moral and legal standards of behavior approved by the people. The legal, cultural and educational influence of folk pedagogy affects the assimilation of the current generation of historically formed legal knowledge, the formation of skills and habits of law-abiding behavior. They ensure the survival and active functioning of the people for a long historical period and in every era [14]. In its vast majority, folk pedagogy and its elements contribute to the establishment of moral and legal behavior, a positive attitude to power, laws, to the protection of the homeland, which in general creates certain prerequisites for the formation of legal consciousness in individuals. At the same time, being an integral product of historical experience, folk pedagogy is conservative in some years and in relation to the events occurring in them. This conservatism can inhibit the acceptance of revolutionary and rapid socio-economic, moral, and legal changes, especially if they fundamentally contradict the historical experience of the people. To a certain extent, this is also found in the conditions of modern Russia. The problem, first of all, is to realize in the theory and practice of legal education the power of the impact of folk pedagogy in the system of other means of formation of legal culture and legal education of citizens in the current situation.

Analysis of contemporary legal documents shows that many of them are based on the eternal postulates of popular pedagogy: recognition of the natural equality of people, the self worth and uniqueness of each individual; rejection of excesses, perversions, torture and self-torture in any sphere; equality of all people before God and the law; respect for the values created by human labor, nature, etc. For folk pedagogy is natural and organic absolute rejection of negative actions. Today many of these provisions have been developed in modern norms of law and are consciously used in legal education [15]. Scientists differently define the concept of legal education, its purpose and significance in the development of society . [16]. Formulated by G. P. Davydov, this concept is first found in the literature in 1959. A. A. Kvasha defines legal education through its constituent elements: "legal education consists in the transmission, accumulation and assimilation of knowledge of the principles and norms of law, as well as in the formation of an appropriate attitude toward the law and the practice of its implementation, the ability to use their rights, comply with prohibitions, and fulfill obligations. Hence the need for a conscious assimilation of the basic, necessary provisions of the law, the development of a sense of deep respect for the law. Acquired knowledge should turn into a personal conviction, into a strong commitment to strictly follow the legal prescriptions, and then - into an internal need to comply with the law. K.V. Naumenkova in her article "Problems of legal education of citizens of Russia at the turn of the century" notes: "Legal education

can be defined as a system of measures aimed at the formation of legal ideas, norms, principles that represent the values of world and national legal culture". [16]. Considering legal education in the context of the theory of state and law, we can say that legal education is an activity of the state, where the main functions are - the maintenance and formation of human behavior, the formation of knowledge of the younger generation, where the basic principles and legal norms will be respected. And in the context of a person legal education is the development of a socially active person, legal thinking and consciousness, the habit of acting in accordance with the laws. The upbringing of the younger generation, in particular legal education, is greatly influenced by the customs and traditions of the peoples. Educational customs and traditions acted as a means of preserving, reproducing, transmitting and consolidating social experience and spiritual values.

They were used to transmit from the elder to the younger the norms of people's behavior and personal requirements. Sometimes the only regulator of social relations of peoples for many centuries was a set of norms of customary law. Customary law as the basis of civilized law is a system of normative self-regulation of a certain community, the limits of which are determined by various factors, among which the legal understanding of this community and its socio-legal needs takes a special place. Customary law has a rich material that can be successfully used for the purposes of legal education of the younger generation. It has many positive aspects: it contributes to the preservation of the identity and culture of the ethnic group, harmonizes relations between its representatives, sometimes fills gaps in the law, facilitates understanding of the law, the law in general and the law of each people in particular. It should be noted that customary law, its customs and traditions have at all times played a positive role in regulating relations both between different peoples and within one and the same ethnos, even within one and the same clan. They have been of great importance in the development and rapprochement of the cultures of different nationalities) [17]. Custom is defined as "a rule firmly established in a particular social environment, which regulates the behavior of people in a certain area of public life. Customs are respected due to their age and repeated, steady application over a long period of time. Tradition (Latin: transmission, tradition) is a way of storing and transmitting social experience (public opinion, mass habits, beliefs, customs) [18]. In the life of every nation, in the life of a public organization, enterprises, institutions, etc., traditions are formed more or less strong, associated with historical conditions of existence, the peculiarities of this or that public collective.

Traditions are characterized by universality, mass character, sustainability, longevity, and emotional appeal. Their strength lies in their natural, partly spontaneous nature. They do not impose views and ways of behavior on anyone, but include the person in practical actions, with which without internal resistance are perceived ideas and norms of actions. Among the ethno-pedagogical traditions of the peoples, which provide legal education, stand out:

- caring attitude towards children, excluding physical punishment, cruelty towards them, combining love, trust in them with demanding performance of their duties;

- inculcation from infancy of a respectful attitude toward parents and the elderly, which helps to overcome the separation of the elderly and the younger, and to establish a generational connection;

- attachment to native places, giving birth to a caring attitude to nature, to the people of their region, developing mental strength, observation, intelligence, the ability to analyze the phenomena of nature, laying the foundation for the formation and development of patriotic feelings;

- participation of children in various kinds of domestic work, which determines the natural community of children and adults, their relationship as equals, the social maturation of children.

Upbringing of independence and overcoming of difficulties in children is combined with careful attitude to them, especially during the infancy. This can be considered a universal quality that to some extent unites all large and small Asian nations. Wherever a child is born, in Japan or Uzbekistan, in Buryatia, in China or Yakutia, in Korea or Turkey, it has a special position in the family. Looking at the methods of popular upbringing, one can find many similarities between the large and small peoples of Asia. Thus, in the system of upbringing of the Japanese people, "upbringing" does not mean scolding for something already done badly, but on the contrary, anticipating bad things, teaching proper behavior. Even in situations that clearly require, if not punishment, at least a reprimand, parents avoid direct condemnation, leaving the child an opportunity to "not lose face". And the most important thing in this system is that bad behavior is not identified with the personality of the child, he or she is instilled with the belief that he or she, of course, can control his or her behavior, if only he or she makes an effort. Instead of nurturing - reprimanding children are taught specific behavioral skills.

It is popularly believed that a child, because of lack of life experience, may make various behavioral mistakes. Children are not punished harshly for their mistakes, because they can become naughty and stubborn. And in the best traditions of upbringing a lot of place is occupied by persuasion, persuasion, shifting attention, etc. Parents don't set out to achieve the end result of parenting at every moment. They constantly indoctrinate children to learn to distinguish right from wrong, good from bad. Therefore, the attitude toward children, especially young children, is very patient. Another factor regulating a child's behavior in Uzbek, Buryat, Tuvian, Evenki and other families is a sense of shame. From a young age, children are inculcated with the idea that if they misbehave, not only they, but also their parents and family members will be laughed at. Many folk traditions, customs, attitudes regulating the behavior of children contribute to the formation of positive qualities of personality. People rightly point out that a person who is cut off from his people, who has not absorbed its culture, is like a tree that has been deprived of its roots. In this context let us consider legal

traditions of the Buryats, which historically developed on the basis of folk customs and were referred to in the literature as customary law or steppe regulations. The written law, which emerged on the basis of customary law, preserved many original traditional legal norms in their original form. Of course, many of those customary legal norms today have acquired relic, archaic forms, having lost the fullness of their former meaning. Others, having passed through time periods, continue to have a certain significance, and sometimes even necessity [19].

Considering the traditions of the peoples, I would like to note that a lot has been preserved in the oral folk epics. The appeal to the historical experience of many nations in the upbringing of children allows you to update the system of formation of personality with lawful behavior and increase the educational potential of the family. Nowadays the future of the nation largely depends on the family upbringing. Therefore, a multilateral and in-depth study of the mechanisms of interaction between generations in the family, its pedagogical potential and resources, its spiritual treasures and moral values is very relevant. The first ideas of the child about the surrounding world, goodness and justice, responsibility and duty are formed in the family. Parental love creates a sense of psychological security. One of the progressive traditions of the Uzbek family is the deep love of parents for their children. It is natural, a trait not only of Uzbeks, but in every nation, it is expressed in a specific form [20]. It is also necessary to take into account that a child's life from birth until adulthood was accompanied by a variety of rituals and ceremonies based on the religious beliefs of the Uzbeks. Often the careful attitude to the child had a religious content. Thanks to such beliefs, many Asian peoples developed a soft, careful attitude to children. A consequence of the love for children is the desire to have many children. A family with many children commands respect. "The more children, the happier the man," says the folk wisdom. Often in families with many children the parents say: "We will raise the older children, and they will raise the younger ones. Until now, the custom of calling parents not by their own names, but by the name of the child, while necessarily indicating that they are the father or mother. In this custom there is reverence for the man who has children. Reasonable love for children is expressed in the fact that their life is defined by a system of strict rules. In a large family, it is possible to cope with all labor duties, to keep the house clean and orderly, and to create a calm and working environment through the fulfillment by all family members of the rules established in the family. Requirements are imposed on children from a young age, and their range expands with age. Certain firm rules of behavior in the family, strict control and unified requirements of the elders are a prerequisite for proper upbringing in folk pedagogy. Children's attitudes toward their parents are characterized by traditional reverence for the father and mother. The folk tradition of honoring parents is closely related to the tradition of respecting elders. The roots of the tradition of respect for elders were generated by the conditions of patriarchal life. The authoritarian nature of the head of the family, the dependence of all family members on his authority, and the unconditional obedience of the younger to the older, all contributed to the development

of respect and obedience to the older. This tradition, at its best, does not preach a cult of personality of the elders or suppress the creative initiative of children.

Respect for elders, as well as other progressive traditions, remaining national in the form of its expression, is based on the recognition of the merits of fathers and grandfathers, on the interest in personality, and involves the perception of the new generation of knowledge, experience and the best traditions of the elders. Respect for elders and parents is expressed in the custom of addressing parents and elders in the family by the word "you". The custom, being an expression of disposition and reverence, fosters a sense of respect for loved ones and skills of polite treatment of people. Children observe the norms of relationships not only in the family, but also in their parents' attitudes toward their children, neighbors, and acquaintances. These norms of Buryat behavior and treatment of each other are expressed in traditional greetings, unhurried questioning about the health of the interlocutor, well-being in the family, wishing luck and success, etc. It is not customary, for example, to hurriedly drop a greeting and pass by. It is customary, respecting the older person, to talk to him leisurely. From childhood, watching the behavior of adults, children adopt them, copying, sometimes without realizing the content, and traditions gradually turn into skills and habits of behavior. Life in the family, regulated by traditions, contributes to a constant exercise in positive behavior, methods of induction are included in family life, the educational position of parents is hidden, their influence is not intrusive, and as a result, the process of education is at ease. Folk pedagogy adheres to the principle of real life education, putting children in different life situations where they act under the influence of established traditions and customs. The methods of apprenticeship and exercises are the main here, folk education goes through assimilation of traditions and customs of the family in practical life. Oral folklore, as a method of persuasion, has been used for centuries in the upbringing of the younger generation. Among the most common types of folklore in the family are proverbs and sayings. Proverbs and sayings in families of many nations have had and still have both cognitive and educational value. Proverbs and sayings teach honesty, diligence, kindness, respect for elders, neatness, thriftiness, etc. Wise thoughts of folk tales, proverbs and sayings influence the formation of ideas about good and evil. Certain opportunities for fostering a culture of behavior of children based on traditions contain oral folk art. Parents' education of children on folk wisdom, proverbs, proverbs reinforce their life experience, serve as a stimulus to show mutual respect for traditions.

On proverbs, proverbs, sayings more than one generation of people have been taught and educated, moreover, some proverbs became a motto in the lives of great men. Folk aphorisms do not just express a particular educational idea, they are created, polished, have as if a definite educational purpose, didactic goals, dictated by the pedagogical intuition of the people, the principle of expediency. First of all, the aphorisms are extremely concise, laconic, short, edifying, easy to remember and serve as a motto in life for young people: "The end of patience is gold", "A good word is sweeter than honey", "A house with children is laughter and a lot of noise, without

children a house is like a prison", "Son and daughter, what your eyes in the forehead", "Mind - with years, education - from childhood". Progressive democratic ideas of great scientists and poets such as Avicenna, Biruni, Jami, Khorezmi, Navoi, Farabi, Khayyam resonated in form and content with the ideas of folk wisdom. Therefore, they had a great influence on the formation of pedagogical culture in Central Asia, and are still relevant today. These scientists expressed the ideas of humanism, emphasized the need to instill in the younger generation high moral qualities, their upbringing in a spirit of love for labor, respect for elders, friendship and comradeship, truthfulness and honesty. Also of interest are numerous good wishes, without which no holiday can do. Wishes are wedding wishes, good wishes for labor (the beginning of sowing, harvesting), on holidays (housewarming, birth of a child), etc. Various folk maxims, preserved today and expressing the ideas of labor traditions, giving advice and rules of labor education, do not contradict, but resonate with modern ideas about the labor training of children: "Happiness is for those who gain intelligence through labor and learning", "Who first in labor, to him the glory everywhere", "Prepared in summer, useful in winter", etc. Among the various methods, techniques and means of folk pedagogy that are used in modern families, we can highlight the following: showing an example worthy of imitation, good advice, teaching, admonition, indirect hint, reminder of the norms of decency, the requirement for their strict observance, teaching to observe the accepted family traditions, exercises in actions, encouragement, praise in the presence of the whole family, punishment, etc. [20]. The Uzbeks, like any other people, in the course of historical experience have developed their ethnic principles, norms and rules of behavior in family and society, which were adopted by each generation from early childhood. Thus, these traditions of upbringing served the function of socialization in reproducing the same moral, family and community norms from generation to generation. One of the main features in upbringing was instilling in children from childhood obedience and respectful attitude to parents, respect and attention. There are such traditional Uzbek legal views, which have been recognized and strictly adhered to by all, as they possess inviolable value in any civil society and are worthy of fixation on constitutional (republican) level of legislation. Such as individual legal responsibility, care for orphans, respect for the elderly, care for parents, a sparing attitude to nature and all living things, a deep understanding of the value of life itself. For centuries, Uzbeks have been working out methods, forms and tools to prepare children for life, which have developed into unique traditions regulating the whole process of upbringing in the family and society. They were formed through regular repetition and transmission from generation to generation and were protected by the force of public opinion.

Such forms and methods of upbringing children as persuasion, positive example and authority of elders, encouragement and punishment, and exercises are practiced. In the Uzbek family proverbs and sayings were widely used as means of persuasion in upbringing, the speech of adults is full of them. They condemn unworthy behavior, dishonesty, boasting, envy, greediness. Proverbs and sayings summarize the life

experience of previous generations and reflect people's views on the formation of personality with lawful behavior [21]. A brief review of folk traditions shows that they serve as a means of legal education: as the traditions of different peoples contain information necessary for the development of the inner world of the student's personality; traditions are learned in figurative, visual-actual or sign-signal (oral or written) form; traditions in the joint activity of the educator and students provide the most important, namely - the manageability of legal education. Manageability is created when: education is an organic part, a natural component of real life and is carried out in the process of solving life tasks; folk traditions, acting as principles, norms, ideals, rules, creating public opinion, develop certain algorithms of human behavior, regulating the life activity.

In our society, there has been a beautiful folk custom since ancient times: when a person or family needs help, then everyone comes to their aid: friends, relatives, neighbors, acquaintances. In the future that person will come to the aid of someone who needs it. The name of this beautiful custom is khashar. Its main principle - mutual assistance and mutual aid - can be expressed in the wise proverb: "One for all, all for one. Hashar is carried out on a voluntary basis. Application of khashar method in construction of dwellings and cultural objects is a remarkable phenomenon that has enriched the best traditions of mutual assistance of many peoples of the Central Asian region. Large objects, irrigation complexes and power systems such as the Farkhad Hydroelectric Power Station, the Kairakum Hydroelectric Power Station, and the Great Fergana Canal have been created by the khashar method. Tashkent, destroyed by the 1966 earthquake, was raised from the ruins in a short time thanks to the friendship and cooperation of different peoples. The norms and rules of culture of behavior have been developed over centuries and millennia as the necessary conditions for the upbringing of an ethnos.

Moral norms of behavior were formulated in the holy books "Qur'an" and "Hadith". They approved or condemned such categories of morality as duty, permission, condemnation, and prohibition, thanks to which they had one or another impact on the level of cultural development of an individual. Therefore, the use of sacred books in the process of education is of great importance in the formation of upbringing. Thus, Hadith, the Koran preaches the introduction of the people's consciousness of the legal, moral, political and other norms of everyday life through various kinds of exhortations, admonitions advice. Over the years of independence, attention and care for the family has risen to the level of state policy. Most importantly, the role of the family in society has been strengthened and its responsibility increased. A strong legal framework has been established with the aim of improving the family as an institution with an important social role. Chapter 14 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is entirely devoted to the family and family relations. Articles 63, 64, 65 and 66 reinforce the rules concerning the role of the family as the basic unit of society, the duty of parents to bring up and support minor children, the duty of adult, able-bodied children to take care of their parents, the protection by the state of

motherhood and childhood, etc. [1, c.46]. In the family, where there is purposeful and painstaking work on the education and spiritual education of children, in the soul and mind of a child grow the sprouts of love and goodness, spirituality and enlightenment. And this will have its positive impact not only on the family, but also in the development process of the whole society.

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